

The Solubility of Lead Monoxide in Perchloric Acid and Hydrolysis of Plumbous Ion

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The solubility of lead monoxide at 30° in perchloric acid of concentrations 0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.08 and 0.06 M has been studied. Lead monoxide does not behave as a normal base and the solubility of lead monoxide in each of the above systems is more than that required for an acid-base reaction. There is an appreciable rise in solubility from 0.1 to 0.2 M solution. The saturated solutions have been subjected to pH titration against standard perchloric acid. The solubility data and the variation of pH with addition of acid are used to investigate the equilibria of the systems.

The system in 0.5 M solution consists of four-fold polymerised ions Pb_4^{2+} , Pb_4^{3+} and Pb_1^{4+} (oxygen, hydrogen and water molecules attached to the ions are not shown) in equilibrium with solid PbO. In the systems in 0.4, 0.3 and 0.2 M perchloric acid, besides the above ions, two fold polymerised ions Pb_2^+ , Pb_2^{2+} and Pb_2^{3+} also exist in equilibrium with the solid. Monomeric ions $PbOH^+$ and Pb^{2+} exist in appreciable amounts in still more dilute solution. Pb_4^{2+} is converted to Pb_4^{3+} and Pb_4^{4+} by stepwise protonation. Similar conversion of Pb_2^+ to Pb_2^{2+} and Pb_2^{3+} by successive protonation and $PbOH^+$ to Pb^{2+} also takes place. Equilibria between Pb_4 and Pb_2 species and between Pb_2 and Pb species exist. The equilibrium constants of various reactions have been determined.

DIVALENT lead forms a number of crystalline salts but with the exception of the nitrate and the acetate, which are incompletely ionised in water, most lead salts are either sparingly soluble or almost insoluble in water. The halides are anhydrous and have complex crystal structure with distorted close packed halogen lattice. The fluoride, PbF_2 , is hydrolysed by steam or even moist air and lead chloride, $PbCl_2$, is hydrolysed at 110°. The study of the behaviour of the plumbous ion Pb^{2+} in solution is difficult.

Akeolin and coworkers¹ have studied the hydrolysis of Pb^{2+} ion in perchlorate medium. The following equilibria have been reported.

The existence of so many types of polymerised ions makes the system very complex to study. The hydrolysis of Pb^{2+} to $PbOH^+$, subsequent polymerisation to $Pb_2(OH)^{3+}$ or $Pb_4(OH)_4^{4+}$ or even higher polymerised ions, followed by the precipitation of hydrated lead oxide is expected to be a continuous process. The opposite effect is expected if PbO is dissolved in acids.

Lead monoxide occurs in enantiotropic forms, a red tetragonal low temperature alpha form and a

yellow high temperature orthorhombic beta form. The crystal structure of the alpha-form has been reported². In lead monoxide Pb-O-Pb layers repeat in the crystal. The oxygen layer is sandwiched between two layers of lead. Each oxygen atom is tetrahedrally joined to four oxygen atoms which are on one side of it forming a square O_4 base. Each Pb atom therefore forms the apex of a $Pb O_4$ pyramid with square O_4 base.

The Pb-O bonds are definitely covalent. There is sp^3d hybridization for the square pyramid arrangement. The apex of the pyramid is occupied by a pair of electrons and the four corners of the square base are occupied by four oxygen atoms.

The covalent nature of Pb-O bonds which is not expected to change in water, is probably responsible for the peculiar type of hydrolysis of plumbous ion.

Experimental

To investigate the species of ions in a saturated solution of lead monoxide in acid solution, the solubilities of lead monoxide in perchloric acid of various concentrations were determined. A known volume of the saturated solution was then titrated against perchloric acid of the same concentration in which lead monoxide was dissolved. The pH of the solution was measured after each addition. B.D.H. sample of lead monoxide was used in the investigation. The lead content of the sample was estimated by sulphate method and was found to contain 99.9%

PbO. AnalaR B.D.H. quality perchloric acid was used. It was standardised against standard 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution.

The solubilities of lead monoxide in perchloric acid of different concentrations were determined. The results are given in Table 1. The square bracket indicates molar concentration. \bar{n} is the average number of protons taken by each lead in solution and is equal to the ratio of $[\text{HClO}_4]$ to $[\text{Pb}]$.

TABLE 1

$[\text{HClO}_4]$	$[\text{Pb}]$	\bar{n}	pH
0.502	0.835	0.601	7.58
0.402	0.657	0.611	7.78
0.301	0.454	0.665	7.88
0.201	0.297	0.679	8.00
0.100	0.0874	1.15	8.20
0.0804	0.0635	1.27	8.22
0.0600	0.0469	1.28	8.24

Results and Discussion

The solubility in each case is more than that required for a simple acid-base reaction. \bar{n} , which is expected to be 2 for an acid-base reaction is less than two in each system. \bar{n} is, however, not constant but increases non-uniformly with increasing dilution; the species of ions are, therefore, expected to change where the variation is appreciable. \bar{n} in the system in 0.502M perchloric acid is 0.601 and hence the average number of protons taken per lead atom is 0.601. Since a fraction of charge cannot be assumed to exist in an ion, polymerised ions containing more than one lead atom have been assumed. If the structure of lead monoxide is examined it appears probable that a unit containing four lead atoms tetrahedrally bonded to a central oxygen atom can be obtained by the degradation of lead monoxide lattice. The structure of the unit can be represented by structure (1) and (2). In this structure there are four lead atoms and 9 oxygen atoms. One of the oxygen atoms is joined to all the four lead atoms, four of them are joined to two lead atoms each and the remaining four are joined to one lead atom each (Fig. 1).

Figure 1

- Pb atom below the plane of oxygen atom.
- Pb atom above the plane of oxygen atom.
- Oxygen atom.

The doubly bonded oxygen atoms would be hydroxyl bridge if each is assumed to have taken a proton. The singly bonded oxygen atoms by taking two protons would be coordinated water molecules. Thus a polymerised ion of composition $\text{Pb}_4\text{O}(\text{OH})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{2+}$ is possible. The hydroxyl bridges of the polymerised ion are successively attacked by the added acid. The proton is added to the hydroxyl bridge and the bridge is broken, the water molecule formed gets attached to one of the two bridged lead atoms and the other lead atom is coordinated with another molecule of water. Thus reaction (2) and

(3) move in the forward direction. The polymerised ions are represented by the number of lead atoms and charge of the ion only. The probable structures of Pb_4^{2+} , Pb_4^{3+} and Pb_4^{4+} are shown in Fig. 2.

If Pb_4 species are assumed to exist in saturated solution of lead monoxide in 0.502M perchloric acid solution, \bar{n} would be four times the value, i.e., 2.405. The formation of Pb_4^{2+} which requires two protons for formation, is complete and a part of Pb_4^{2+} is converted to Pb_4^{3+} and Pb_4^{4+} . The probable reactions are therefore :

The constant K_{b4} cannot be calculated at this stage. The reactions (2) and (3) are stepwise protonation reactions and K_1 and K_2 can be obtained from the formation curves³.

The saturated solutions obtained with different concentrations of perchloric acid have been subjected to pH titration with perchloric acid of the same concentration. The overall \bar{n} has been calculated by assuming the species to be Pb_4 and Pb_2 in systems in 0.502, 0.401, 0.301 and 0.201M perchloric acid and monomeric in the more dilute systems. \bar{n} is obtained by dividing the total acid consumed (acid initially present + acid added - acid present in the solution after the reaction) by the concentration of Pb_4 or Pb_2 or Pb .

In the above reactions the formation of Pb_4^{2+} has been assumed to be complete. Hence the actual \bar{n} for reactions (2) and (3) is two less than the overall \bar{n} . In Fig. 3 \bar{n} is plotted against pH. Curves, (A), (B), (C), and (D) are obtained for the systems in 0.502, 0.402, 0.301 and 0.201M perchloric acid respectively. The major part of the curves (A) and (B), very nearly coincide. The curves (C) and (D) are similar but are away from the curves (A) and (B). It is probable that besides the reactions already proposed some

Figure 2

other reactions are also involved in systems in 0.301 and 0.201M perchloric acid.

The system in 0.502M perchloric acid is expected to consist of Pb_4 species. The approximate values

Figure 3

of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ obtained from the formation curve are 7.18 and 5.98 at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$ respectively. The corrected values obtained by Schroder method³ are 6.95 and 6.14 respectively.

If the ionic species in the solution are tetrameric, the concentrations of the ions Pb_4^{2+} , Pb_4^{3+} and Pb_4^{4+} can be calculated from the total concentration of tetrameric ions $[Pb_4]$, pH , K_1 and K_2 .

$$[Pb_4] = [Pb_4^{2+}] + [Pb_4^{3+}] + [Pb_4^{4+}]$$

or

$$[Pb_4^{2+}] = \frac{[Pb_4]}{1 + K_1[H^+] + K_1 \times K_2[H^+]^2} \quad \dots (4)$$

The concentrations of Pb_4^{3+} and Pb_4^{4+} can be similarly calculated. Calculation shows that in the system in 0.301M acid only 15% of the total lead exists in tetrameric form at pH 7.68. Hydrolysis and protonation of a tetrameric ion is expected to yield two dimeric ions. The proton requirement per lead for the formation of Pb_2^+ from lead monoxide is 0.5. \bar{n} in the saturated solutions of lead monoxide in 0.301 and 0.201M perchloric acid is greater than 0.5. If these solutions are assumed to contain appreciable amount of dimeric ions the formation of Pb_2^+ would be complete and part of it would be converted to Pb_2^{2+} and Pb_2^{3+} by stepwise protonation reaction.

If the coordination of lead(II) is retained in the dimeric ions also, the composition of the above ions would be $Pb_2O(OH)(H_2O)_4^+$, $Pb_2(OH)_2(H_2O)_4^{2+}$ and $Pb_2OH(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ (Fig. 4). The average water requirement per lead atom being more for the dimeric ions than that for the tetrameric ions, the dimeric ions are expected to exist in less concentrated solutions and the system in 0.20 M acid would consist mostly of dimeric ions. Hence besides, reactions (1), (2) and (3) the following equilibria also exist in the saturated solutions of lead monoxide in 0.301 and 0.201M perchloric acid solution :

Due to the addition of acid to the saturated solution of lead monoxide in perchloric acid the reactions (6) and (7) move in the forward direction. The acid also produces dilution effect which progressively decreases the tetrameric species present in the solution. The system in 0.201M perchloric acid is expected to consist of dimeric ions at least towards the

Figure 4

latter part of the experiment. To determine the values of K_3 and K_4 , \bar{n} is plotted against pH in Fig. 5. The curves (A) and (B) represent the systems in 0.301 and 0.201M perchloric acid. As expected the two curves do not coincide. The system in 0.201M acid being more favourable for equilibria of dimeric ions only, the approximate values of $\log K_3$ and $\log K_4$

Figure 5

obtained from curve (B) are 7.42 and 5.74 and the values corrected by Schroder method are 7.49 and 5.75 respectively.

The solubility of lead monoxide in 0.1M or less concentrated perchloric acid is comparatively less and \bar{n} is greater than one. The ionic species in these solutions are expected to be different from those found in more concentrated solution. The ions are assumed to be hydrated Pb^{2+} and $PbOH^+$.

The reactions are represented by

The system in 0.1M perchloric acid might be containing polymerised ions to a certain extent

besides the ions $PbOH^+$ and Pb^{2+} . The increase in the value of \bar{n} from the system in 0.08M acid to that in 0.06M acid being very small the ionic species in this region do not change appreciably. It is therefore assumed that the systems in 0.08M and 0.06M perchloric acid, and specially the latter, consist of monomeric ions.

In Fig. 6 actual \bar{n} has been plotted against pH . Curves (A) and (B) represent the system in 0.1 and 0.06M perchloric acid respectively. The two curves, as expected, do not coincide. The value of $\log K_5$ obtained from curve (B) is 6.84.

Co-relation of the solubilities :

The solubility of lead monoxide in 0.06M perchloric acid is 0.0469 moles per litre and the pH of the solution is 8.24. Hence, $[Pb] = 0.0469$.

Figure 6

$$[Pb] = [PbOH^+] + [Pb^{2+}]$$

or

$$[PbOH^+] = \frac{[Pb]}{1 + K_5 \times [H^+]} \quad \dots (10)$$

$[Pb]$ and pH being known, $[PbOH^+]$ is obtained from equation (10). K_{b1} which is equal to $[PbOH^+]/[H^+]$ is calculated, $\log K_{b1}$ is found to be 6.19. A better constant can be obtained by using the value of \bar{n} in the saturated solution of lead monoxide in 0.06M perchloric acid, \bar{n} being 1.28.

$$[Pb^{2+}] = [Pb] \times 0.28, \text{ and } [PbOH^+] = (1 - 0.28)[Pb]$$

Using the value of $[PbOH^+]$, $\log K_{b1}$ is found to be 6.77. The latter value is taken to be the most probable value.

In the saturated solution of lead monoxide in 0.502M and 0.402M perchloric acid, the predominating ions are tetrameric. The tetrameric ions are also expected to be in appreciable amounts in the saturated solution of lead monoxide in 0.301 and 0.201M perchloric acid. As a first approximation the above saturated solutions are assumed to consist of only tetrameric ions. The concentration of Pb₄ is one fourth the solubility. [Pb₄²⁺] is calculated from equation (4). Kb₄ which is equal to [Pb₄²⁺]/[H⁺]² is calculated using the value of [Pb₄²⁺] and pH. The values are given below.

TABLE 2

[HClO ₄]	pH	[Pb ₄]	[Pb ₄ ²⁺]	log Kb ₄
0.502	7.68	0.209	0.175	14.60
0.402	7.78	0.164	0.143	14.71
0.301	7.88	0.133	0.102	14.77
0.201	8.00	0.0744	0.0683	14.83

Kb₄ gradually increases with dilution. The increase is due to increasing amount of dimeric ions in more dilute solutions. 14.60 is taken as the most probable value of log Kb₄. Using this value and the pH, [Pb₄²⁺] was calculated for the systems in 0.402, 0.301 and 0.201M perchloric acid. [Pb₄] was then calculated by equation (4). Subtracting the calculated [Pb₄] from the experimental value, the amount of Pb₄ converted to Pb₂ was obtained. [Pb₂⁺] was calculated as follows by equation (11).

$$[Pb_2] = [Pb_2^+] + [Pb_2^{2+}] + [Pb_2^{3+}]$$

or

$$[Pb_2^+] = \frac{[Pb_2]}{1 + K_3[H^+] + K_3 \times K_4[H^+]^2} \quad \dots (11)$$

Kb₂ which is equal to [Pb₂⁺]/[H⁺] was calculated and is given below :

TABLE 3

[HClO ₄]	pH	[Pb ₄ ²⁺]	[Pb ₄]	[Pb ₂]	[Pb ₂ ⁺]	log Kb ₂
0.402	7.78	0.110	0.126	0.0381	0.0251	6.18
0.301	7.88	0.0692	0.0773	0.0361	0.0256	6.29
0.201	8.00	0.0398	0.0434	0.0399	0.0305	6.48

The value of log Kb₂ increases slightly with dilution. This might be due to the presence of monomeric ions. 6.18 is taken as the most probable value of log Kb₂.

Equilibria between Pb₄, Pb₂ and Pb species of ions :

The Pb₄ species are progressively converted to Pb₂ species and Pb₂ species to Pb species on dilution.

Some type equilibria are expected to exist for such conversion. The conversion takes place on protonation or hydrolysis, or both. The examination of the proposed structure of Pb₄²⁺ indicates that this structure can only break to dimeric ion on protonation. The following equilibria have been proposed.

The concentrations of Pb₄²⁺, Pb₂⁺ and PbOH⁺ can be expressed in terms of equilibrium constants and concentration of hydrogen ions. Thus

$$Pb_4^{2+} = Kb_4 H^{+2}, \quad Pb_2^+ = Kb_2 H^+,$$

$$\text{and } PbOH^+ = Kb_1 H^+.$$

The concentration of the other ions can be calculated in terms of equilibrium constants and H⁺ using the value of Pb₄²⁺ or Pb₂⁺ or PbOH⁺ given above. The values of Ka₁, Ka₂, etc., would be as follows :

$$Ka_1 = \frac{Kb_2^2 \times K_3}{Kb_4}; \quad Ka_2 = \frac{Kb_2^2 \times K_3^2}{Kb_4 \times K_1}$$

$$Ka_3 = \frac{Kb_2^2 \times K_3^2}{Kb_4 \times K_1 \times K_2}; \quad Ka_4 = \frac{Kb_1^2}{Kb_2 \times K_3}$$

$$Ka_5 = \frac{Kb_1^2 \times K_5}{Kb_2 \times K_3}; \quad Ka_6 = \frac{Kb_1^2 \times K_5^2}{Kb_2 \times K_3 \times K_4}$$

Hence

$$\log Ka_1 = 5.25, \log Ka_2 = 5.76, \log Ka_3 = 0.38, \\ \log Ka_4 = -0.13; \quad \log Ka_5 = 6.71 \text{ and} \\ \log Ka_6 = 7.80.$$

References

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